
Wisdom of the crowd—What’s the most important food crop

Is the collective opinion of a group of people more valuable than that of a single expert? I don’t know. What do you think?

This is the last post of 2022. Let’s have some fun.

What’s the most important food crop

The peer-reviews of our paper “[A pandemic clonal lineage of the wheat blast fungus](#)” are in, just in time before the winter holidays break. The verdict is positive, but one reviewer took offence with the opening sentence: “Wheat, the most important food crop, is threatened by a blast disease pandemic.” They wrote that according to Google, rice, not wheat, is the most important food crop. Fair enough. But what does the crowd think? Let’s ask the Twitterverse.

Wheat vs rice. Discuss.

The responses—36 at last count—ranged from “[the cultivation of wheat in the Middle East was the factor that jump-started the whole European Civilization. So, yeah, wheat,](#)” to “[half the world’s population eat rice at least once a day,](#)” and not to forget “[based on gross production in biomass, it’d be corn/maize](#)”.

The potato people somehow kept quiet with [just one mention](#). But, there was the usual semi-serious and tongue-in-cheek replies that pitched anything from [millet](#), [sugarcane](#), [Arabidopsis](#), [raspberry](#), [oat](#), [olive](#), [pistachio](#), [almond](#), [barley](#) and [strawberry](#).

ChatGPT, the remarkably articulate AI engine, was more reasonable than most tweeps: “[It is difficult to choose just one food crop as the most important, as different crops are important to different regions and cultures around the world, and the importance of a particular crop can also vary depending on the context,](#)” it wrote.

When asked the very specific question, ChatGPT wouldn’t take sides, “[both rice and wheat are important food crops,](#)” it stated.

LJ

Reviewer 3: Wheat, the most important food crop? When I Google crops, rice comes up as the number one food crop.

Discuss.

It is true that rice is the most widely consumed staple food for a large part of the world's population, especially in Asia. According to data from the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO), rice is the world's second most produced cereal crop, with over 790 million metric tons produced in 2019. Wheat is the third most produced cereal crop, with around 765 million metric tons produced in the same year.

However, it is worth noting that different regions of the world have different dietary patterns and consumption patterns of various food crops. Wheat is a major food crop in many countries and is an important source of nutrients for millions of people around the world. It is the most widely grown cereal grain and is a staple food in many parts of the world. In fact, wheat is considered the most important food crop in some countries, such as the United States and Canada, where it is the primary grain used to make bread, pasta, and other baked goods. Wheat is also used to make other products such as cereal, flour, and alcoholic beverages.

In summary, both rice and wheat are important food crops that are widely consumed around the world. While rice is the most widely consumed staple food in many parts of the world, wheat is also a major food crop and is an important source of nutrients for many people. The relative importance of these crops may vary depending on the region and cultural dietary patterns.

[ChatGPT wouldn't take sides on the wheat vs rice debate.](#)

There was the wise people who [objected to the reviewer's use of Google](#), referred to [FAO statistics](#), and pointed out that [an affinity for vodka could influence of reviewer's perspective](#). I'm not so sure about that last one; you can make [superb alcoholic drinks with rice](#). And you can also cook with rice based sake—a somewhat irrelevant sentence I added simply to give myself an excuse [to post a photo of this fish kinmedai \(金目鯛, splendid alfonsino, *Beryx splendens*\)](#). Isn't it splendid?

[The review was written under the influence of vodka.](#)

[Kinmedai \(金目鯛, splendid alfonsino, *Beryx splendens*\) cooked in rice-based sake.](#)

There was only one solution to sort out this divergence of views once for all. A “scientific” Twitter poll. And the Final Results are in: [rice is the most important food crop](#).

Tell reviewer 3 what’s the most important food crop?

305 votes · Final results

[Twitter polls tap into the wisdom of the crowd 🤖](#)

Who can argue with such an unambiguous outcome. We will have to revise the paper accordingly. In fact, our trusted editor [Jen Mach](#) suggests [deleting that first sentence altogether](#).

[Ditch “X is the most important...” Wise advice by Jen Mach.](#)

There is a fungus among us

Jen is absolutely right. Let's just ditch the throwaway "[X is the most important...](#)". Can't we just agree that both rice and wheat are very important food crops that are so critical to feeding the planet? Which leads me to the blast fungus pathogen; it happens to cause recurrent epidemics on both of these essential food crops. It's an important plant pathogen, okay. I won't say any more.

Research article | [Open Access](#) | [Published: 16 July 2020](#)

Differential loss of effector genes in three recently expanded pandemic clonal lineages of the rice blast fungus

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BMC Biology, 18, Article number: 88 (2020)

A pandemic clonal lineage of the wheat blast fungus

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3 pandemic clones
~100s years old

1 pandemic clone
~15 years old

The blast fungus causes pandemic diseases on both rice and wheat. Check our [openriceblast](#) and [openwheatblast](#) portals.